

FLD trials and they adopted these in the succeeding years, resulting in enhanced productivity. The yield of rice, however, varied because of climate changes during the experimental period and the use of different varieties.

The observed technology gap may be attributed to dissimilarities in soil fertility, salinity, and weather conditions. Hence, a location-specific recommendation appears to be necessary to close the gap. The wide extension gap emphasizes the need to educate farmers. The technology index reflects the feasibility of using the evolved technology in farmers' fields. The lower the value of the

technology index, the more feasible the use of the technology is. The highest technology index, noted in 1997 kharif with variety CSR10, clearly indicates the existence of a wide gap between technologies developed at research stations and those used in farmers' fields.

Additional costs, mainly for inputs, were noted in the FLD trials, thus increasing the cost of cultivation over that of the local check. But gross returns and net returns were still substantial in the FLD trials. Higher benefit-cost ratios were seen with improved varieties than with local checks (Table 3).

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Table 3. Economics of rice cultivation.

Year	Variety	Cost of cultivation (Rs ha ⁻¹)				Gross return (Rs ha ⁻¹)		Net return (Rs ha ⁻¹)			Benefit-cost ratio	
		Input cost for demonstration (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Demonstration	Local check	Additional cost of cultivation in demonstration (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Demonstration	Local check	Demonstration	Local check	Additional return (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Demonstration	Local check
1997	CSR10	2,372	9,768	8,525	1,243	17,300	13,115	7,532	4,590	2,942	0.77	0.53
1998	Parvel 1	2,372	8,883	7,900	983	18,800	14,400	9,917	6,500	3,417	1.11	0.82
1999	Parvel 1	2,372	12,166	10,900	1,266	20,900	17,200	8,699	6,300	2,309	0.71	0.57

Extent of women's involvement in Indian rice cultivation

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As in other countries, nearly half of the available human resources in India are women. In traditional village communities, women are primarily involved in all stages of crop cultivation, from field preparation to harvesting of grains. In rural areas of India, most female workers help the men in farm operations, especially in the agricultural sector (Sherwani 1983). In general, women provide 60–70% of labor input. For rice, this pro-

portion reaches 80%. Gautam and Meenakshi (1992) indicated that the proportion of women in the agricultural labor force was more and their contribution to agriculture was greater than men's.

In 2000, we conducted a study at the Regional Research Station, Paiyur, to find out the extent of women farmers' involvement in rice cultivation. The data were collected at Palacode and Krishnagiri taluks of Dharmapuri

District in Tamil Nadu, India. Agriculture is the source of livelihood of the people in this area, with a wide variety of crops grown—cereals, millet, pulses, oilseeds, tomato, and mango. In this district, rice is grown on about 57,000 ha of land during the wet (Jul–Nov) and dry seasons (Dec–Mar). Canal and well-irrigation systems are fairly common.

One hundred and twenty women farmers were selected

randomly from six villages in these two taluks (20 from each village). Most of the women farmers cultivate relatively small farms (0.1–1 ha); some who have more land (>1 ha) live in clusters. Through a well-structured interview schedule, data on the involvement of women in each cultivation practice were collected. The extent of involvement of women farmers was categorized

into three groups: doing the work herself, assisting, and supervising.

Women farmers were actively involved in all rice cultivation practices, except in the preparation of the field for transplanting (22% reporting) and raising seedlings in nurseries (34% reporting) (see table). These practices are considered risky and therefore involve only men. Simi-

larly, spraying of pesticides and fungicides to protect the crop is regarded as an all-male activity. Women farmers did not want to be involved as they perceived this activity to be risky (100%). Women were highly involved in transplanting (79.2%), intercultivation (59.8%), harvesting (82.7%), and postharvest (89.6%) operations.

Extent of women's involvement in rice cultivation, Dharmapuri District, Tamil Nadu, India.

Cultivation practice	Doing the work herself		Assisting		Supervising		Others ^a	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
<i>Main field preparation</i>								
Collecting stubbles	15	12.5	–	–	30	25.0	75	62.5
Cleaning field boundaries	10	8.3	–	–	15	12.5	95	79.2
Applying farmyard manure	–	–	15	12.5	20	16.7	85	70.8
Plowing and leveling	–	–	–	–	–	–	120	100
Subtotal	25	5.2	15	3.1	65	13.6	375	78.1
<i>Nursery preparation</i>								
Seed cleaning	–	–	28	23.3	32	26.7	60	50.0
Seed treatment	–	–	5	4.2	18	15.0	97	80.8
Sowing	10	8.3	–	–	30	25.0	80	66.7
Subtotal	10	2.8	33	9.2	80	22.2	237	65.8
<i>Transplanting</i>								
Pulling out seedlings	62	51.7	13	10.8	22	18.3	23	19.2
Transporting seedlings	58	48.3	17	14.2	–	–	45	37.5
Transplanting in main field	58	48.4	25	20.8	30	25.0	7	5.8
Subtotal	178	49.5	55	15.3	52	14.4	75	20.8
<i>Intercultivation</i>								
Gap filling	42	35.0	5	4.2	35	29.2	38	31.6
Weeding	48	40.0	10	8.3	40	33.3	22	18.4
Applying herbicides	–	–	15	12.5	32	26.7	73	60.8
Topdressing fertilizers	–	–	20	16.7	40	33.3	60	50.0
Subtotal	90	18.8	50	10.4	147	30.6	193	40.2
<i>Plant protection</i>								
Spraying pesticides/fungicides	–	–	–	–	–	–	120	100
Subtotal	–	–	–	–	–	–	120	100
<i>Harvesting</i>								
Harvesting	60	50.0	24	20.0	36	30.0	–	–
Bundling	48	40.0	–	–	60	50.0	12	10.0
Transporting to yard/thrashing floor	28	23.3	10	8.3	–	–	82	68.4
Heaping	60	50.0	18	15.0	40	33.3	2	1.7
Thrashing	52	43.3	12	10.0	48	40.0	8	6.7
Subtotal	248	41.3	64	10.7	184	30.7	104	17.3
<i>Postharvest</i>								
Winnowing	40	33.3	5	4.2	60	50.0	15	12.5
Bagging	38	31.7	12	10.0	60	50.0	10	8.3
Stacking	40	33.3	18	15.0	45	37.5	17	14.2
Storing	112	93.3	–	–	–	–	8	6.7
Subtotal	230	47.9	35	7.3	165	34.4	50	10.4
Total	781	27.1	252	8.8	693	24.1	1,154	40.0

^aReasons given for not being involved in rice cultivation: no time to get involved, hired laborers to do the job, considered it risky, and regarded it as man's job.

Sixty percent of the women farmers were directly involved in rice cultivation, distributed in each category as follows: doing the work herself (27.1%), assisting (8.8%), and supervising (24.1%). They played a distinct and well-accepted role in such activities as pulling out seedlings (80.8%), transporting (62.5%), transplanting seedlings (94.2%), harvesting (100%), bundling (90%), heaping the bundles (98.3%), thrashing (93.3%), win-

nowing (87.5%), bagging (91.6%), and storing of grains (93.3%). Women farmers with small land did the activities themselves to reduce cultivation costs and thereby increase net income. On the other hand, women farmers with big farms often paid others to assist in and supervise the process of cultivation.

The results imply that technology development and transfer should consider specific characteristics and needs of women in

the conduct of rice production activities. This will enhance efficiency in different farming operations and boost farm productivity and net profit.

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Farmers' participatory evaluation of BRRI hybrid dhan 1 in Bangladesh

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Farmers' participatory evaluation of rice varieties refers to the active involvement of farmers in the process of selecting varieties. It enables one to understand the criteria and approaches used by farmers in deciding what variety to grow (Hawlader 2001). BRRI hybrid dhan 1, the first hybrid rice variety developed by the BRRI and released in 2001, was evaluated using a participatory approach at on-station (BRRI Regional Station, Bhanga, Faridpur) and on-farm (13 villages of Faridpur District) trials in 2002 boro (dry season). In many countries, this approach is commonly used to identify farmers' preferred varieties. In Nepal, varieties selected through participatory evaluation yielded 15–18% more than existing varieties (Sthapit et al 1996). In view of the very little work done on participatory

evaluation of hybrid rice in Bangladesh, this study used a participatory approach to learn farmers' preferences and opinions about hybrid rice.

On-station trials evaluated BRRI hybrid dhan 1, three imported hybrids (Sonar Bangla, Alook, and Jagoron), two popular inbred varieties (BINA dhan 5 and BINA dhan 6), and one popular inbred check variety (BRRI dhan 29). All the test varieties were grown side by side with the check variety. Plot size was 20 m × 10 m. The on-farm experiment used BRRI dhan 29, a popular boro rice variety, as a check for comparison with BRRI hybrid dhan 1. Plot size was 20 m × 20 m. Forty-day-old seedlings of each variety were transplanted at a spacing of 20 cm × 15 cm with 1–2 seedlings per hill. Standard agronomic practices were followed.

Field evaluation of crop cuts of test and check varieties was done at crop maturity. Farmers, officials of the Directorate of Agricultural Extension and Seed Certification Agency, BRRI scientists, newspaper reporters, and local leaders were present at the occasion. Through brainstorming sessions, group discussions, and matrix rankings, 200 participating farmers identified the characters of a rice hybrid that they preferred.

Results of on-station trials revealed that BRRI hybrid dhan 1 took 163 d to mature and its grain yield was 8.2 t ha⁻¹ (Table 1). BRRI hybrid dhan 1 exhibited the highest productivity (50.3 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹), followed by BRRI dhan 29 (44.6 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹), Sonar Bangla (44.5 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹), and Alook (38.4 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹). BRRI hybrid dhan 1 showed a 12.8% increased productivity over BRRI dhan 29.